

Argumentative Causal Discovery over TECHINT

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Abstract

The contemporary cyber threat landscape is increasingly shaped by automation, artificial intelligence, and the strategic deployment of advanced persistent threats (APTs). These multi-stage intrusions unfold over time, requiring defenders not only to detect malicious activity but also to understand its progression and underlying causal structure. Traditional intrusion detection systems, which often rely on binary classification, fail to capture the temporal and interdependent nature of such attacks. This technical note combines time-series causal inference with argumentation-based reasoning to render causal claims explicit, interpretable, and subject to structured scrutiny. The approach operates in two stages: first, the LPCMCI algorithm is applied to infer candidate causal relations among events and system states; second, each inferred link is evaluated dialectically, with arguments generated both in favour of and against the causal claim. By integrating algorithmic inference with formal argumentation, the method transforms opaque causal graphs into transparent, contestable artefacts.

1 Introduction

The contemporary cyber threat landscape is characterised by an expanding attack surface, the integration of automation and Artificial Intelligence (AI) into offensive operations, and the increasing sophistication of targeted intrusions. Among these, Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs) remain particularly challenging due to their stealth, persistence, and strategic objectives [1, 22]. APT campaigns unfold over extended periods, progressing through multiple stages such as reconnaissance, delivery, exploitation, and command-and-control [11]. Understanding how these stages manifest in observable behaviour is critical for timely detection and effective response.

Traditional intrusion detection approaches often focus on binary classification — distinguishing benign from malicious activity. However, this coarse-grained perspective overlooks the temporal and causal structure of attacks. Defensive strategies depend not only on knowing that an intrusion is underway but also on understanding where the adversary is in their operational lifecycle and how observed behaviours influence one another over time. For example, the appearance of lateral movement following privilege escalation suggests a causal progression that can inform containment priorities. Conversely, treating events as isolated signals risks misinterpretation and delayed mitigation.

Technical Intelligence (TECHINT)—including network telemetry, endpoint logs, and malware execution traces—offers a rich but complex substrate for such analysis. These data streams are inherently temporal, reflecting sequences of actions and system responses. Capturing the behavioural patterns embedded in these sequences requires moving beyond correlation-based analytics toward causal discovery over time series: identifying which events or conditions are likely to influence others and in what order. Causal models provide a structured representation of dependencies among observables, enabling analysts to reason about attack dynamics, anticipate next steps, and evaluate counterfactual scenarios (*e.g.*, “What if this connection had been blocked earlier?”).

This technical note combines time-series causal inference with argumentation-based reasoning to make causal claims explicit, interpretable, and contestable.

Our approach proceeds in two stages:

1. **Time-series causal graph induction using Latent Peter-Clark Momentary Conditional Independence (LPCMCI).** We apply the LPCMCI algorithm to TECHINT streams to infer candidate causal relations among events and system states, producing a directed graph that encodes hypothesised behavioural links.
2. **Dialectical evaluation of causal claims.** Each candidate edge becomes an object of structured debate: arguments are generated for the link and against it [14, 4].

By integrating causal discovery with formal argumentation, this work—which builds upon [7, 8, 6, 3, 5]—aims to bridge the gap between algorithmic inference and human-understandable justification. Rather than treating causal graphs as opaque outputs, we expose the reasoning behind each link, enabling analysts to contest, refine, or accept causal claims in light of domain knowledge and operational constraints. This hybrid approach enhances situational awareness by revealing not just what is happening, but why—a prerequisite for proactive and adaptive cyber defence.

2 Background

2.1 CyberBattleSim: A Virtualised Cybersecurity Testbed

The CyberBattleSim framework¹ developed by Microsoft constitutes a substantive advancement in the domain of cybersecurity research. It provides a virtualised environment specifically designed to facilitate controlled experimentation and the development of cyber defence capabilities. Constructed atop the OpenAI Gymnasium (Gymnasium) architecture, the platform abstracts the complexity inherent in real-world networks by representing systems as nodes

¹<https://github.com/microsoft/CyberBattleSim> (accessed on 15 July 2025)

within a graph structure. This abstraction significantly lowers the barrier to entry for researchers and practitioners, obviating the necessity for a fully operational network infrastructure.

Within this simulated environment, agents governed by Reinforcement Learning (RL) algorithms emulate adversarial behaviour, executing a range of actions aimed at compromising system integrity. These actions encompass both localised exploits—such as the extraction of passwords and exposure of credentials—and remote attacks targeting vulnerable nodes. Upon successful compromise, agents may engage in lateral movement across the network using protocols such as Secure Shell (SSH) and Remote Desktop Protocol (RDP) [13].

CyberBattleSim has demonstrated considerable utility in cyber defence training and competitive scenarios, including capture-the-flag exercises. Its principal advantage lies in its capacity to function as a cyber-specific *physics engine*, offering dynamic feedback that static datasets are unable to provide. This feature is particularly salient in contexts requiring rapid decision-making and the cultivation of incident response competencies [18, 2].

2.2 Formal Representations of Adversarial Behaviour: Attack Models

Attack models serve as formal abstractions of adversarial strategies, encapsulating the objectives pursued by attackers, the decision points encountered, and the sequences of Tactics, Techniques, and Procedures (TTP) employed throughout an intrusion. By articulating these behavioural patterns in a structured format, such models enable security teams to anticipate potential threat trajectories, simulate attack scenarios, and evaluate the effectiveness of existing defensive controls.

The MITRE Corporation (MITRE) ATT&CK Flow² offers a systematic framework for the visualisation and analysis of adversarial operations. It employs a

²<https://center-for-threat-informed-defense.github.io/attack-flow> (accessed on 15 July 2025)

flowchart-based schema to interconnect discrete TTP elements derived from the ATT&CK knowledge base, thereby elucidating the progression of an attack across its lifecycle. This structured mapping enhances organisational understanding of threat dynamics, facilitates the identification of defensive gaps, and supports the refinement of detection and mitigation strategies.

By fostering shared situational awareness, the ATT&CK Flow framework contributes to the development of more resilient security postures and promotes collaborative approaches to threat intelligence.

2.3 Attack Stages and Reward Machines

The task of classifying the stage of an attack may be conceptualised as the inference of an adversary's abstract progression through a sequence of behavioural states, based on observed actions. This process is analogous to determining the latent state of a Reward Machine (RM) governing a RL agent within a given environment—such as an attacker pursuing a defined objective.

A *RM* is a finite-state automaton employed to define structured reward functions for RL agents [12]. It comprises the following components:

- **States:** abstract constructs representing the agent's advancement through a task.
- **Transition function:** logical rules dictating state changes based on environmental observations.
- **Labelling function:** a mapping from low-level features to symbolic propositions used in transition conditions.

Reward machines enhance the expressiveness of task definitions and improve the interpretability of agent behaviour. They also support the transfer of learned policies across structurally analogous tasks. In the context of cybersecurity, this abstraction allows attacker behaviour to be modelled in terms of symbolic subgoals—akin to phases in the cyber kill chain—while abstracting away low-level artefacts such as system logs or process telemetry

(**observations**). The labelling function transforms these artefacts into symbolic indicators (**labels**) that may signal the onset of a new attack phase. For instance, in the Uber breach, the compromise of an external contractor's credentials (symbolic label) enabled subsequent lateral movement (new attack stage).³

This modelling approach is particularly effective in honeypot environments. Unlike production systems, where benign activity predominates and malicious behaviour is sporadic, honeypots are designed to attract and isolate unauthorised interactions. Consequently, the observed action sequences in honeypots are typically devoid of legitimate behaviour and consist solely of adversarial traces. This reduction in behavioural variance simplifies the inference task, as all recorded activity is relevant to attack stage classification. The attacker's actions may thus be interpreted as the trajectory of a RL agent operating within a known environment, with RM states corresponding to distinct phases of the adversary's strategic logic.

2.4 Causal Discovery

Causal discovery seeks to identify causal relationships from observational data, typically under a set of structural assumptions. A foundational framework for such reasoning is provided by Judea Pearl's theory [15, 16, 17], which formalises causality using graphical models and structural equations.

Pearl's formalism is commonly referred to as a Structural Causal Model (SCM), or alternatively as a Directed Graphical Causal Model (DGCM). This framework integrates a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) with a joint probability distribution, encoding assumptions about direct causal mechanisms and conditional independencies within the system.

Definition 2.1 (Structural Causal Model). A SCM is defined as a tuple $\mathcal{M} = \langle \mathcal{G}, \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{F}, P(U) \rangle$, where:

³<https://center-for-threat-informed-defense.github.io/attack-flow/ui/?src=..%2fcorpus%2fUber%20Breach.afb> (accessed on 11 June 2025).

- $\mathcal{G} = (V, E)$ is a DAG, with each node $X_i \in V$ representing a variable.
- \mathcal{X} denotes the set of possible values for the variables.
- $\mathcal{F} = \{f_i : \text{Pa}(X_i) \times U_i \rightarrow X_i\}$ is a collection of structural functions, one per variable, where $\text{Pa}(X_i)$ refers to the parents of X_i in \mathcal{G} and U_i is an exogenous noise term.
- $P(U) = \prod_i P(U_i)$ is a product distribution over the exogenous variables.

Each endogenous variable X_i is determined by the equation $X_i := f_i(\text{Pa}(X_i), U_i)$.

Definition 2.2 (Intervention and do-calculus). Given a SCM \mathcal{M} and a variable $X_i \in V$, an intervention $\text{do}(X_i = x)$ yields a modified model $\mathcal{M}_{\text{do}(X_i=x)}$ in which the structural function f_i is replaced by the constant function $f_i := x$, and the distribution over the remaining variables is updated accordingly.

Definition 2.3 (Causal Bayesian Network). A Causal Bayesian Network (CBN) is a pair (\mathcal{G}, P) where:

- \mathcal{G} is a DAG.
- P is a joint probability distribution over the variables, satisfying the *Markov condition*: each variable is conditionally independent of its non-descendants given its parents.

2.5 D-separation and Faithfulness

Conditional independencies within a graph are interpreted using the concept of d-separation.

Definition 2.4 (D-separation). Let \mathcal{G} be a DAG, and let X , Y , and Z be disjoint sets of nodes. A path between a node in X and a node in Y is said to be *blocked* by Z if:

- The path contains a *non-collider* node that is in Z . A node v is a non-collider if the path traverses it via $u \rightarrow v \rightarrow w$, $u \leftarrow v \leftarrow w$, or $u \leftarrow v \rightarrow w$.

- The path contains a *collider* node v (i.e., $u \rightarrow v \leftarrow w$), and neither v nor any of its descendants are in Z .

We say that X is *d-separated* from Y given Z if all paths between nodes in X and Y are blocked by Z .

Definition 2.5 (Causal Markov Assumption). A distribution P over variables V satisfies the *Causal Markov Assumption* with respect to a DAG \mathcal{G} if each variable is conditionally independent of its non-descendants given its parents.

Definition 2.6 (Causal Faithfulness Assumption). A distribution P is said to be *faithful* to a DAG \mathcal{G} if every conditional independence observed in P is implied by d-separation in \mathcal{G} .

2.6 Constraint-Based Discovery: The PC Algorithm

Assuming both the Causal Markov and Faithfulness assumptions hold, causal structure can be inferred by testing for conditional independencies in the data. A prominent method in this category is the Peter-Clark (PC) algorithm [21].

The PC algorithm is *sound* under the aforementioned assumptions and *point-wise consistent* in the limit of large sample sizes, provided there are no latent confounders. Its output is a Completed Partially Directed Acyclic Graph (CPDAG), representing the Markov Equivalence Class (MEC) of all DAGs consistent with the observed independencies.

Despite its popularity, the PC algorithm has several limitations. Firstly, it assumes the absence of hidden confounding variables and selection bias—an assumption often violated in practical domains such as healthcare, economics, or machine learning diagnostics. Unobserved confounders may introduce spurious associations or obscure genuine causal links, undermining the reliability of the inferred structure.

Secondly, the algorithm depends heavily on statistical tests for conditional independence. These tests guide edge removal and v-structure orientation, but are susceptible to both Type I (false positive) and Type II (false negative) errors,

particularly in finite samples. Conditioning on large variable sets increases variance, and weak or non-linear dependencies may be difficult to detect, potentially leading to unstable or incorrect graph structures.

Thirdly, the PC algorithm cannot distinguish between different DAGs within the same MEC. It returns a CPDAG, which encodes a set of graphs sharing identical d-separation properties. While theoretically sound, this limits the interpretability of the output, as many edges remain unoriented without further assumptions or interventional data.

Finally, from the standpoint of formal argumentation, the algorithm is purely syntactic: it interprets statistical dependencies without regard to the semantic meaning of the edges. Each link is treated as a probabilistic artefact rather than a domain-informed causal hypothesis. This poses challenges in contexts where causal claims must be justified, interpreted, or contested. Accordingly, there is a growing need for frameworks that support the articulation and critical evaluation of causal assertions—link by link—through structured arguments, explanations, and counter-arguments. Such approaches can complement statistical discovery by making the assumptions and domain-specific implications of each inferred relationship explicit and open to scrutiny.

2.7 Constraint-Based Causal Discovery with PCMCI and LPCMCI

The Peter-Clark Momentary Conditional Independence (PCMCI) algorithm [19] is a constraint-based approach to causal discovery, specifically designed to infer causal networks from large-scale, interdependent time series data. It achieves this by accurately selecting conditioning variables to improve the reliability of independence testing. The method comprises two key stages:

- Initially, the algorithm applies PC_1 —a variant of the PC algorithm [20]—to identify appropriate conditioning sets for each time series variable, based on their parent sets.
- Subsequently, a Momentary Conditional Independence (MCI) test is conducted to determine whether two variables are conditionally independent.

dent, given their respective parent sets.

These stages serve distinct purposes: the first eliminates irrelevant conditioning variables through iterative testing, while the second mitigates false positives arising from strong autocorrelations typical of time series data.

The PCMCI framework operates under several assumptions: causal sufficiency, the Causal Markov and Faithfulness conditions, stationarity, and the absence of contemporaneous causal effects.

The LPCMCI algorithm [10] extends PCMCI to accommodate latent confounding. While PCMCI enhances statistical power by refining conditioning sets during the MCI step, LPCMCI further constrains these sets to known ancestors and augments them with default conditions derived from identified parents. This design improves stability in conditional independence testing when hidden common causes are present.

A distinctive feature of LPCMCI is the use of *middle marks* in its graphical representation. These marks encode intermediate causal information during execution, enabling early and accurate edge orientation by capturing partial ancestor–descendant relationships. Unlike traditional methods that separate edge removal and orientation, LPCMCI integrates these steps, ensuring interpretability throughout the graph refinement process.

The algorithm proceeds iteratively, beginning with a fully connected graph and progressively refining it. In the initial phase, spurious edges are removed using Conditional Independence (CI) tests that benefit from increased effect sizes due to default conditioning. Simultaneously, middle marks guide early orientation decisions. In the final phase, remaining erroneous edges are pruned, and orientations are finalised using additional statistical tests and refined graphical rules.

Under standard assumptions—faithfulness and sufficient sample size—LPCMCI is both sound and complete, reliably reconstructing the true Partial Ancestral Graph (PAG). Its ability to incorporate latent confounders while improving recall and reducing false positives makes it particularly suitable for high-dimensional and temporal datasets.

In our study, LPCMCI was employed in conjunction with a specific MCI test: the Gaussian Process Distance Correlation (GPDC) test [?], a nonparametric method for assessing conditional independence $X \perp\!\!\!\perp Y \mid Z$ in continuous-valued settings. The procedure decomposes the problem into two stages: regression followed by dependence testing. Let $(X, Y, Z) \in \mathbb{R}^{d_X} \times \mathbb{R}^{d_Y} \times \mathbb{R}^{d_Z}$ be random variables with an unknown joint distribution. Under the null hypothesis, X and Y are independent given Z , and their conditional expectations can be modelled as:

$$X = f_X(Z) + \varepsilon_X, \quad Y = f_Y(Z) + \varepsilon_Y, \quad (1)$$

where ε_X and ε_Y are residuals satisfying $\mathbb{E}[\varepsilon_X \mid Z] = \mathbb{E}[\varepsilon_Y \mid Z] = 0$. If the null holds, the residuals should be mutually independent.

The functions f_X and f_Y are estimated nonparametrically using Gaussian process regression, allowing for flexible modelling of complex dependencies. Once fitted, the residuals $\hat{\varepsilon}_X$ and $\hat{\varepsilon}_Y$ are computed and transformed to variables r_X and r_Y with uniform marginals via rank-based normalisation. The test statistic is the distance correlation:

$$\mathcal{R}(r_X, r_Y) = \frac{\mathcal{V}^2(r_X, r_Y)}{\sqrt{\mathcal{V}^2(r_X, r_X) \mathcal{V}^2(r_Y, r_Y)}}, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathcal{V}^2(\cdot, \cdot)$ denotes the squared population distance covariance. At the population level, $\mathcal{R}(r_X, r_Y) = 0$ if and only if r_X and r_Y are independent, ensuring theoretical consistency. For finite samples, this property holds asymptotically under regularity conditions such as ergodicity or strong mixing.

The statistical validity of the GPDC test depends on the asymptotic behaviour of the distance correlation under the null. However, due to the nonparametric nature of the regression and the transformations involved, the null distribution of $\mathcal{R}(r_X, r_Y)$ is not analytically tractable. Consequently, significance is assessed via permutation or resampling-based approximations. While theoretically robust, the practical application of GPDC is challenged by high-dimensional conditioning: when the conditioning set is large relative to the sample size, Gaussian process regression may fail to capture conditional struc-

ture adequately, reducing the test to an approximate measure of unconditional dependence. These limitations will be explored further in future work.

2.8 Argumentative Structures Supporting Causal Claims

Causal reasoning plays a pivotal role across a wide range of disciplines, including scientific research, public policy, and engineering, where practitioners seek to justify why a particular outcome (the effect) arises from a preceding condition or event (the cause). This section presents a structured typology of argumentative forms that support or challenge causal assertions, building upon the frameworks proposed in [14, 4].

2.8.1 Circumstantial Evidence

Arguments based on circumstantial evidence appeal to observed regularities or proximity between events, without necessarily invoking mechanistic or counterfactual reasoning. Such arguments typically adopt the form:

“*A* caused *B* because *A* regularly precedes or co-occurs with *B*, or resembles other known causes of *B*.”

Several subtypes of circumstantial evidence may be distinguished:

Spatio-temporal contiguity The cause and effect are observed in close spatial or temporal proximity, suggesting a potential causal link through their juxtaposition.

Repeated co-occurrence The events consistently appear together across multiple instances, indicating a statistical regularity that may warrant further causal investigation.

Analogical similarity The scenario under consideration shares salient features with previously established causal cases. If *A* and *A'* are analogous, and *A'* is known to cause *B*, then by analogy, *A* may plausibly be inferred to cause *B*.

These forms of evidence are inherently provisional and typically serve as heuristic devices for hypothesis generation or preliminary empirical exploration.

2.8.2 Contrastive Evidence

Contrastive arguments rely on observed differences in outcomes under varying conditions, and are generally structured as:

“*A* caused *B* because *B* occurs when *A* is present, but not when *A* is absent.”

The following subtypes are commonly encountered:

Statistical covariation A measurable divergence in outcomes is observed between groups or conditions, which persists after controlling for confounding variables. This contrast is interpreted as indicative of a causal role for the varying factor.

Before–after comparison An intervention or change is introduced, followed by a discernible shift in outcomes. Provided other factors remain stable, the observed change is attributed to the intervention.

Controlled experiment All variables are held constant except for the one under investigation. A consistent difference in outcomes across conditions is then attributed to the manipulated variable.

2.8.3 Causal Explanation

Causal explanations aim to articulate the mechanism by which a cause brings about its effect, offering greater explanatory depth than correlational or contrastive arguments. These are typically framed as:

“*A* causes *B* because *A* initiates a sequence of intermediate steps that culminate in *B*.”

The principal subtypes include:

Mechanistic explanation The argument specifies a concrete sequence of interactions or processes—often grounded in physical, computational, or biological theory—through which the cause produces the effect.

Elimination of alternatives Competing explanations are systematically ruled out. If the effect coincides exclusively with changes in A , and other variables are held constant, A is inferred to be the most plausible cause.

Typicality of effect The observed outcome conforms to patterns typically associated with similar causes in analogous contexts, thereby reinforcing the credibility of the proposed mechanism.

2.9 Argumentative Structures Opposing Causal Claims

Arguments that challenge causal assertions may be broadly categorised into two groups: those that question the plausibility of the proposed causal relationship, and those that critique the logical coherence or sufficiency of the justification provided.

2.9.1 Plausibility-Based Objections

This class of argument contests the credibility of the causal link in light of empirical or conceptual considerations. Several subtypes may be identified:

Incorrect temporal ordering The purported effect precedes the alleged cause, thereby violating the fundamental principle that causes must temporally precede their effects.

Lack of connection The proposed cause and effect pertain to unrelated domains, or no plausible mechanism exists to link them. In the absence of a credible pathway, the causal claim remains unsupported.

Autonomous decision The outcome results from an independent choice or intervention, not causally determined by the proposed factor. The alleged cause is incidental rather than explanatory.

Insufficient cause The proposed factor fails to consistently produce the effect, indicating that it cannot, in isolation, account for the observed outcome and may require additional enabling conditions.

Redundant cause The effect is fully explicable by other known causes. The proposed factor is therefore superfluous, diminishing its causal relevance.

2.9.2 Logical Objections

Logical critiques target the inferential structure of the causal argument, identifying weaknesses in reasoning or proposing more plausible alternatives. The principal subtypes include:

Alternative explanation The observed association may be more convincingly attributed to a third variable that influences both the proposed cause and the effect.

Post hoc fallacy The argument erroneously infers causality from mere temporal succession, assuming that because B follows A , A must have caused B , without further evidential support.

Weak statistical evidence The effect is observed inconsistently or with low frequency. A limited correlation or low base rate undermines the robustness of the causal claim.

Anecdotal basis The argument relies on isolated or atypical instances, which are insufficient for generalisation and susceptible to confounding or noise.

Absence of mechanism No account is provided of how the proposed cause leads to the effect. In the absence of a plausible mechanism, the claim remains speculative.

2.9.3 Qualification of Causal Assertions

Certain arguments do not reject the causal claim outright but instead refine its interpretation by clarifying its scope, strength, or contextual dependencies. These qualifications include:

Partial causation The proposed factor contributes to the outcome but is neither the sole nor the dominant cause. Other influences are likely to play a more significant role.

Indirect causation The effect arises through a sequence of intermediate steps, rather than as a direct consequence of the proposed cause.

Common causation Both the proposed cause and the observed effect stem from a shared underlying factor, suggesting that the true causal origin lies elsewhere.

Interaction effects The proposed factor exerts a causal influence only in conjunction with other conditions. In isolation, its impact may be negligible.

Reversed causality The direction of influence is misrepresented; what is presented as the cause may in fact be a consequence of the effect.

Coincidental association The observed causal link is accidental, arising from an unrelated or unforeseen event that occurred simultaneously.

2.10 Using LLMs for Arguing in Favour and Against Causal Links

To enhance the interpretability and epistemic robustness of data-driven causal discovery, we adopt the methodology introduced in [3], which integrates structured argumentative reasoning into the causal inference workflow. Following the identification of candidate causal relationships—typically obtained via structure learning algorithms—we proceed to critically assess each inferred link through the generation of structured arguments both in support of and in

- 1 Given the causal claim: [INSERT CAUSAL CLAIM],
2 produce a structured argument *in support* of this claim. Choose
3 only one among the following argumentation strategies:
4
5 1. Circumstantial Evidence:
6 - Provide at least one argument using spatio-temporal contiguity,
7 repeated co-occurrence, or similarity to known causes.
8
9 2. Contrastive Evidence:
10 - Provide at least one argument based on statistical covariation,
11 before-after comparison, or a controlled experiment.
12
13 3. Causal Explanation:
14 - Provide at least one mechanistic explanation, argument from no
15 alternative explanation, or an argument based on typical effect.
16
17 Each argument must:
18 - Clearly state which macro-family and specific subtype it belongs
19 to.
20 - Be logically self-contained and persuasive.
21 - Refer explicitly to the observed or hypothesised phenomena.
22 - Be concise.

Listing 1: Prompt Template: Argue in Favour of a Causal Link

opposition to the claim. This process is facilitated by Large Language Models (LLMs), which are prompted to produce arguments aligned with a typology of causal reasoning patterns. Specifically, we elicit responses corresponding to macro-families of causal justification: *circumstantial evidence*, *contrastive evidence*, and *causal explanation* for affirmative claims; and *plausibility challenges*, *logical objections*, and *qualifications* for critical ones. The prompt templates used to generate these arguments are detailed in Listings 1 and 2.

This argumentative evaluation serves a dual purpose. First, it provides a transparent rationale for each causal assertion, thereby improving interpretability and facilitating domain-specific scrutiny. Second, it enables the identification of weak or unsupported claims by juxtaposing competing argumentative structures. To further refine the assessment, we introduce a dialectical adjudication phase, wherein the LLM is prompted to compare opposing arguments and

- 1 Given the causal claim: [INSERT CAUSAL CLAIM],
2 produce a structured argument *against* this claim. Choose only one
3 among the following argumentation strategies:
- 4 1. Plausibility Challenges:
5 - Include at least one argument based on wrong temporal order, no
6 plausible connection, free decision,
7 insufficient cause, or unnecessary cause.
- 8 2. Logical Objections:
9 - Include at least one argument from alternative cause, post hoc
10 fallacy, low statistical support,
11 anecdotal evidence, or unknown mechanism.
- 12 3. Qualifying Claims:
13 - Optionally include partial, indirect, common cause, interaction,
14 reversed causality, or accidental cause qualifications.
- 15 Each argument must:
16 - Identify the macro-family and the specific argumentation subtype.
17 - Be articulated as a counterpoint to a potential or actual
18 supporting argument.
19 - Indicate whether the causal claim is to be rejected, weakened, or
reformulated.
- Be concise.

Listing 2: Prompt Template: Argue Against a Causal Link

render a judgement on the overall plausibility of the causal claim. This final stage, described in Listing 3, requires the model to classify each input argument by macro-family and subtype, evaluate its logical and evidential strength, and conclude with one of four verdicts: (i) the claim is accepted as likely, (ii) tentatively accepted with caveats, (iii) deemed undecidable pending further evidence, or (iv) rejected. This structured adjudication ensures that argumentative quality is systematically integrated into the causal evaluation process, thereby mitigating the risk of premature acceptance of claims derived solely from statistical structure learning.

- 1 You are given two arguments regarding the same causal claim.
2
3 Causal Claim:
4 [INSERT CAUSAL CLAIM]
5
6 Argument in Favour:
7 [INSERT PRO-CASUAL ARGUMENT HERE]
8
9 Argument Against:
10 [INSERT COUNTER-ARGUMENT HERE]
11
12 Task:
13 Evaluate the overall credibility of the causal claim based on the
two arguments. Your judgment must:
14
15 1. Reference the strength and relevance of the macro-family and
subtype for each argument.
16 2. Indicate whether the causal claim should be:
17 - Accepted as likely
18 - Tentatively accepted with caveats
19 - Undecided or requiring more evidence
20 - Rejected
21 3. Justify your decision with explicit reference to the comparative
argumentative strength (\eg directness, generalisability,
mechanistic plausibility, alternative explanations).
22 4. Avoid introducing new arguments - focus only on evaluating the
two provided.
23
24 Output format:
25 - Summary judgment (one sentence)
26 - Justification (3-5 sentences)

Listing 3: Prompt Template: Final Judgement on a Causal Link

3 Identifying Behavioural Indicators

3.1 Switched LAN CTF Scenario

A simulated switched Local Area Network (LAN) was constructed to emulate a Capture The Flag (CTF) scenario, wherein an adversary initiates from a predefined entry node and must ultimately compromise a designated target device. All nodes within the network are fully interconnected, thereby enabling unrestricted lateral movement across devices.

To successfully reach the target—representing a high-value asset such as a database or server—the attacker must first acquire a valid access credential. Both the credential node and the goal node are randomly assigned at the beginning of each simulation instance.

The target device is safeguarded by an Intrusion Prevention System (IPS), which actively monitors for unauthorised access attempts. Any effort to reach the target without the appropriate credential results in immediate failure. Consequently, the attacker must explore the network to locate a valid credential prior to attempting exploitation of the goal node.

The attack sequence is modelled using the MITRE ATT&CK Flow framework, which delineates the adversary's progression and operational stages, as illustrated in Figure 1. From this behavioural model, a corresponding RM is derived (Figure 2), incorporating two symbolic labels: **c** for credential acquisition and **g** for goal exploitation.

This switched LAN CTF environment was selected for experimentation due to its encapsulation of key elements observed in real-world cyber intrusions—namely credential theft, lateral movement, and target exploitation—while retaining sufficient simplicity to support preliminary analysis.

Figure 1: Representation of the Switched LAN environment using MITRE ATT&CK Flow.

Figure 2: Reward Machine for the Switched LAN CTF, with two symbolic labels: **c**redentials acquired and **g**oal achieved.

3.2 Dataset Acquisition

The dataset employed in this study was originally introduced in [9], and was generated using a simulated environment based on CyberBattleSim.

The input data comprises two principal components: agent observations of the environment's state and the outputs of the labelling function.

The observation space is defined as the union of all valid preconditions for each vulnerability present in the network. This representation prioritises exploitability conditions over mere positional data, resulting in a significantly expanded observation space relative to simpler models. Explicit action data is omitted, as each state transition is uniquely determined by a single action. Thus, the dynamics of state changes inherently encode the performed actions, rendering their explicit inclusion superfluous.

Labelling function outputs are incorporated into the dataset for two key reasons. Firstly, they provide contextual enrichment, aiding the model's comprehension of the environment. Secondly, they allow for the simulation of noise

within the labelling process, which is essential for evaluating the robustness of the approach under realistic conditions where labelling may be imperfect.

3.3 Causal Analysis

In this study, we employed the LPCMCI algorithm to infer causal structure from continuous-valued time series data, under the presence of potential latent confounding. The method was configured to operate with a GPDC test as its conditional independence criterion. This nonparametric test is particularly well-suited to capturing complex, nonlinear dependencies without imposing restrictive parametric assumptions.

The analysis — whose results are shown in Figure 3 — was conducted under a fixed temporal lag structure, and a conservative significance threshold was adopted to ensure robustness against false positives. The integration of GPDC within the LPCMCI framework allowed for enhanced sensitivity in detecting causal links, especially in high-dimensional settings where traditional independence tests may suffer from reduced statistical power. The resulting causal graph reflects a refined structure obtained through iterative pruning and orientation, guided by the algorithm's use of middle marks and default conditioning strategies. This approach enabled early and interpretable edge orientation, while maintaining theoretical soundness under standard assumptions of faithfulness and sufficient sample size.

3.4 Critical Evaluation of LLM Output on Causal Claim

To demonstrate the methodology and the type of results that can be obtained through argumentative evaluation of causal links, we focus in this paper on a single claim: “The acquisition of credentials by an attacker moving within a network cause almost immediately that the attacker would then leverage the credentials to authenticate to the target device.”

Figure 3: Causal Graph Generated with LPCMCI. Labels' names in line with Figures 1 and 2.

1 Chosen Strategy: Causal Explanation -> Mechanistic Explanation
2 Argument Type: Causal Explanation - Mechanistic Explanation
3
4 Claim: The acquisition of credentials by an attacker moving within a network almost immediately causes the attacker to leverage those credentials to authenticate to the target device.
5
6 Argument:
7
8 Mechanism: Once an attacker obtains valid credentials, these credentials act as authentication tokens within the network's access control system. The attacker can now bypass perimeter defences and directly request sessions with the target device using standard authentication protocols (e.g., Kerberos, NTLM). This process is automated in most attack toolkits (e.g., Mimikatz, Cobalt Strike), which immediately attempt authentication upon credential acquisition.
9
10 Why Immediate: The automation of credential use is a core feature of lateral movement tools. These tools are designed to minimise detection by reducing dwell time; thus, they initiate authentication attempts as soon as credentials are harvested. There is no rational delay because the attacker's objective is to escalate privileges or reach high-value assets quickly before being detected.
11
12 Observed Phenomenon: Incident response reports (e.g., MITRE ATT&CK case studies) consistently show that credential dumping is followed almost instantly by authentication attempts to other hosts, confirming the mechanistic link between acquisition and use.
13
14 Conclusion: The causal link is supported by the operational mechanism: credential acquisition directly enables and triggers authentication attempts, and this process is typically immediate due to automation and attacker incentives.

1 Macro-family: Plausibility Challenges

2 Subtype: Free Decision

3

4 Counterpoint:

5 A supporting argument might assert:

6 "Once an attacker acquires credentials, they will almost immediately
use them to authenticate to the target device."

7

8 Rebuttal:

9 The causal link assumes deterministic behaviour, ignoring the
attacker's autonomy. Attackers often delay or refrain from
immediate credential use to avoid detection, plan lateral
movement, or prioritise other objectives. Thus, the acquisition
of credentials does not necessarily cause immediate
authentication.

10

11 Impact on Claim:

12 Weakened - the claim overstates inevitability and immediacy.

13

14 Macro-family: Plausibility Challenges

15 Subtype: Wrong Temporal Order

16

17 Counterpoint:

18 A supporting argument might claim:

19 "Credential acquisition precedes authentication, so it must cause it
. "

20

21 Rebuttal:

22 In some intrusion scenarios, attackers first establish authenticated
sessions through other means (e.g., exploiting trust
relationships) and only later collect credentials for persistence
. This reverses the assumed temporal order, undermining the claim
that acquisition is the immediate cause.

23

24 Impact on Claim:

25 Weakened - the temporal sequence is not universally valid.

- 1 Summary judgment: The causal claim should be tentatively accepted with caveats.
- 2
- 3 Justification: The argument in favour is strong in mechanistic plausibility and directness: it details a well-documented operational mechanism (credential acquisition enabling immediate authentication) and cites automation as a driver of immediacy, supported by empirical evidence from incident reports. However, the counterarguments under the Plausibility Challenges macro-family are relevant and credible: the Free Decision subtype highlights attacker autonomy, introducing variability that undermines determinism, while the Wrong Temporal Order subtype demonstrates that the assumed sequence is not universal. These rebuttals reduce the generalisability of the claim, showing that immediacy is common but not inevitable. Therefore, while the mechanistic explanation supports the claim as likely in many cases, its overstatement of inevitability requires qualification.

Listing 6: LLM-generated final judgment on the causal claim, balancing both sides.

We utilised Microsoft Copilot, which is powered by OpenAI's GPT-5 large language model. GPT-5 is a state-of-the-art transformer-based model trained on a mixture of licensed data, data created by human trainers, and publicly available text. It supports advanced natural language understanding, reasoning, and multi-step problem solving. The model operates in a decoder-only architecture with attention mechanisms and is optimised for conversational and task-oriented interactions.

Listing 4 provides a mechanistic causal argument supporting the claim that credential acquisition by an attacker almost immediately leads to authentication attempts. The reasoning is grounded in the operational behaviour of lateral movement tools, which automate credential use to minimise detection. The use of standard authentication protocols such as NT LAN Manager (NTLM) and Kerberos, and the reference to tools like Mimikatz and Cobalt

Strike, reinforces the plausibility of the causal link. The argument is further strengthened by empirical evidence from incident response reports, including those catalogued by MITRE, which consistently document immediate credential use following acquisition.

Listing 5 introduces two counterarguments under the macro-family of Plausibility Challenges. The Free Decision subtype challenges the deterministic framing of the claim by highlighting attacker autonomy. It correctly notes that attackers may delay credential use for strategic reasons, such as avoiding detection or prioritising other objectives. The Wrong Temporal Order subtype presents scenarios where authentication precedes credential acquisition, particularly in sophisticated intrusions involving trust exploitation. These counterpoints are credible and relevant, demonstrating that the causal sequence proposed in the claim is not universally valid and may be reversed in certain APT scenarios.

Listing 6 synthesises the arguments and counterarguments, offering a balanced judgment that tentatively accepts the causal claim with caveats. It acknowledges the mechanistic strength and empirical support of the pro argument, while integrating the variability introduced by attacker autonomy and alternative temporal sequences. The conclusion that immediacy is common but not inevitable reflects a nuanced understanding of adversarial behaviour in network intrusions. This qualified acceptance avoids overgeneralisation and aligns with the probabilistic nature of causal inference in cybersecurity contexts.

The three listings collectively illustrate the value of structured argumentative evaluation in assessing causal claims. Listing 4 excels in mechanistic clarity, Listing 5 introduces necessary scepticism, and Listing 6 models a reasoned adjudication process. This methodology is particularly well-suited to cybersecurity, where causal relationships are often contingent on strategic behaviour, operational constraints, and incomplete observability.

4 Conclusion

This report has introduced a hybrid framework for causal analysis over TECHINT, combining time-series causal discovery via LPCMCI with dialectical reasoning to produce interpretable and contestable causal claims. By embedding causal inference within an argumentative structure, the approach addresses a critical gap in cyber defence: the need not only to detect adversarial behaviour but to understand its underlying dynamics and justify analytical conclusions. The resulting causal graphs are not merely algorithmic artefacts but structured hypotheses subject to scrutiny, refinement, and operational validation.

Future work will explore the integration of LLMs to enhance both stages of the framework. In causal graph induction, LLMs may assist in feature selection, temporal abstraction, and the contextual enrichment of TECHINT streams, particularly when dealing with heterogeneous or incomplete data. More significantly, LLMs can support the dialectical evaluation of causal claims by generating, ranking, and critiquing arguments based on threat intelligence corpora, attack playbooks, and system documentation. This would enable a more scalable and context-aware argumentative layer, where machine-generated reasoning complements human expertise without supplanting it.

To assess the practical utility of the proposed framework, future work might include a structured evaluation with domain experts. This will involve presenting causal graphs and associated arguments to experienced analysts, measuring interpretability, trust, and decision support efficacy. Such evaluation will also inform the refinement of argument templates and the calibration of causal thresholds. Ultimately, the goal is to develop a robust decision-support tool that augments human reasoning in cyber defence operations, fostering proactive and adaptive responses to complex threats.

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Acronyms

- AI** Artificial Intelligence. 2
- APT** Advanced Persistent Threat. 2, 27
- CBN** Causal Bayesian Network. 7
- CI** Conditional Independence. 10
- CPDAG** Completed Partially Directed Acyclic Graph. 8, 9
- CTF** Capture The Flag. 20, 21
- DAG** Directed Acyclic Graph. 6–9
- DGCM** Directed Graphical Causal Model. 6
- GPDC** Gaussian Process Distance Correlation. 11, 22
- Gymnasium** OpenAI Gymnasium. 3
- IPS** Intrusion Prevention System. 20
- LAN** Local Area Network. 20
- LLM** Large Language Models. 17, 28

LPCMCI Latent Peter-Clark Momentary Conditional Independence. 3, 10, 11, 22, 23, 28

MCI Momentary Conditional Independence. 9–11

MEC Markov Equivalence Class. 8, 9

MITRE MITRE Corporation. 4, 20, 27

NTLM NT LAN Manager. 26

PAG Partial Ancestral Graph. 10

PC Peter-Clark. 8, 9

PCMCI Peter-Clark Momentary Conditional Independence. 9, 10

RDP Remote Desktop Protocol. 4

RL Reinforcement Learning. 4–6

RM Reward Machine. 5, 6, 20

SCM Structural Causal Model. 6, 7

SSH Secure Shell. 4

TECHINT Technical Intelligence. 2, 3, 28

TTP Tactics, Techniques, and Procedures. 4, 5